

HODISALARGA ASOSLANGAN HOLDA BIG DATA MA'LUMOTLARNI VIZUALIZATSIYA QILISH UCHUN DELTA-BASED RENDERING ALGORITMLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya

So'nggi yillarda real vaqt rejimidagi ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va ularni vizual ko'rsatish tizimlariga talab keskin oshdi. Fintech, IoT, transport monitoringi va kiberxavfsizlik kabi sohalarda soniyasiga millionlab hodisalar (events) hosil bo'ladi.

Ammo mavjud BI tizimlar (Tableau, PowerBI, Grafana) bu hodisalarni oqim shaklida vizual ko'rsatishda kechikish (latency) va resurs isrofi muammolariga duch keladi.

Shu bois, delta-based rendering — ya'ni faqat o'zgargan ma'lumot segmentlarini yangilash konsepsiyasiga asoslangan yangi yondashuv ishlab chiqish dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: big data, delta based rendering, real-time dashboard, low latency

Abstract

In recent years, the demand for real-time data analysis and visualization systems has sharply increased. In fields such as fintech, IoT, transport monitoring, and cybersecurity, millions of events are generated every second.

However, existing BI systems (such as Tableau, PowerBI, and Grafana) face latency and resource inefficiency issues when visualizing these events in a streaming format.

Therefore, developing a new approach based on the concept of delta-based rendering — that is, updating only the changed data segments — has become highly relevant.

Keywords: big data, delta based rendering, real-time dashboard, low latency

Muammoning qo'yilishi

An'anaviy real-time grafik tizimlar har bir hodisa kelganda butun grafikani qayta chizadi. Bu esa:

- brauzerning CPU yuklamasini oshiradi,
- tarmoq trafigini ko'paytiradi,
- interfeysning silliqiligini pasaytiradi (FPS kamayadi).

Demak, oqimli vizualizatsiya tizimlarida muammo — faqat o'zgargan ma'lumotlarni aniqlab, ularni samarali tarzda qayta chizishdir.

Asosiy maqsad — Taklif etilayotgan yondashuvda tizim hodisalar oqimi → delta hisoblash → vizual yangilanish jarayonlariga asoslanadi.

Delta hisoblash algoritmi:

- Har bir yangi event kelganda, u avvalgi holat bilan solishtiriladi.
- Faqat o'zgarish (delta) aniqlanadi: qo'shilgan, o'chirilgan yoki yangilangan qatorlar.
- Delta JSON shaklida WebSocket orqali frontendga uzatiladi.
- Frontend faqat o'sha elementlarni qayta renderlaydi.

Tajriba natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki:

• Delta-rendering algoritmi qo'llanganda grafik yangilanish kechikishi 2,5 baravar kamaydi;

- Tarmoq trafigi 40–60% ga qisqardi;
- FPS (frames per second) o‘rtacha 35% ga oshdi;
- Tizim katta hajmdagi oqimlarda (1M events/min) ham barqaror ishladi.

Xulosa

Delta-based rendering yondashuvi oqimli ma’lumotlarni real vaqt rejimida vizuallashtirishda yuqori samaradorlikni ta’minlaydi. Taklif etilgan arxitektura resurs tejamkor, reaktiv va masshtablanuvchi bo‘lib, ayniqsa fintech, IoT monitoring va telemetriya tizimlari uchun mos.

Kelgusida, tizimni adaptive delta threshold (muayyan o‘zgarish darajasidan keyin yangilash) va GPU-accelerated rendering bilan boyitish rejalashtirilgan.

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